

ARCHAEOLOGICAL SURVEY OF ISLAMIC SITES
IN SOUTHERN IRAN 1969-1970.

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Archaeological survey was carried out in the winter of 1969, when work was curtailed by illness, and was continued in 1970 as part of The British Institute of Persian Studies' research project on Islamic trade and settlement in Southern Iran, and in cooperation with Dr. Whitehouse's excavations for The British Institute of Persian Studies at Siraf. This survey was a continuation of research carried out in 1968-1969, on which an interim report has been previously presented to the Iranian Archaeological Service, and the results of which will be published with the work described below.

The aims of this research are:

- a) To plot the distribution and size of settlement on the Persian Gulf coast in the Sassanian and Islamic Periods, especially in the Early Islamic period represented in the excavations at Siraf.
- b) To plot the distribution by trade of Islamic and Sassanian pottery types, especially those represented in the excavations at Siraf.
- c) To investigate the trade routes leading inland from the Persian Gulf coast, and to record the trade in pottery along these routes.

Representative samples of pottery have been collected from all sites visited. These are presently housed in the site museum at Siraf, with a view to their preservation as a reference collection.

The pottery from the Pre-Sassanian sites discovered in the course of this research is being handed over to Professor C. C. Lamberg-Karlovsky of Harvard University, who, in view of his survey work in Kerman Province and his excavations at Tepe Yahya, is well equipped to deal with the information.

The writer has been assisted throughout this research by Martha Prickett of Harvard University and Fellow of the National Science Foundation, Washington, D.C..

It is intended in the months of March and April 1971 to study and classify this material. When this is completed, a full gazetteer and list of sites, giving size, location, details of pottery, and the periods of occupation will be provided for the use of the Iranian Archaeological Service to aid in further research.

The following report provides information on the most important sites, pending the preparation of a complete final report.

The areas investigated archaeologically were:

- a) The region of Jiruft and the route from Bam to Minab.
- b) The Minab oasis.
- c) The region of Bandar-i Tahiri.
- d) The Bushehr Peninsula.

a) The Region of Jiruft and the Route from Bam to Minab.

Three major Islamic and Sassanian sites and twelve of lesser importance were investigated in a brief survey from Bam to Minab through the Jiruft.

3.6 km. due East of the village of Darzin, 23 km. West of Bam on a low site known as Tarikistan Islamic pottery dating from the 3rd to 11th centuries A.H. is scattered over an area of 3,500 m. by 1,200 m..

On the well known site of Shahr-i Daqianus, 2 km. West of Sabzevaran, Jiruft, pottery scatter covers an area of 5 km. by 6 km. and is predominantly composed of white bodied glazed and unglazed moulded pottery of the 5th and 6th centuries A.H..

95 km. South of Sabzevaran and immediately South of the village of Tump-i Kharg, a large Sassanian mound known as Tump-i Kharg rises 10 m. high beside the Halil Rud and covers an area of 450 m. by 400 m.. Lower mounding extends 1,000 m. by 700 m.. The pottery on the site is exclusively Sassanian, except for an area of 300 m. by 400 m. on the South West with Early Islamic, and a small fortress 80 m. square with pottery of the 7th to 8th centuries A.H..

In addition Pre-Sassanian sites recorded in Sir M. A. Stein's book, Archaeological Reconnaissances in North-Western India and South-Eastern Iran, were revisited. Two newly discovered mounds with early material were found in the Jagin plain, 36 km. from Minab. Tump-i Mehdar, 1.3 km. South West of Cheraghabad village, is a mound 120 m. in diameter, rising 12 m., with Islamic pottery overlying that of the 3rd and 1st millennia B.C.. 1.5 km. beyond

Tump-i Mehdar a site 6 m. high and occupying an area of 350 m. by 370 m. had surface pottery of the 4th to 5th millennia B.C.

b) The Minab Oasis.

157 sites were located in the Minab oasis. They comprised 11 Pre-Sassanian sites, 8 Sassanian sites, and 145 sites with Islamic surface pottery. Two of the Sassanian sites were of particular importance. The first, 250 m. by 190 m., rises 3 m. high in barren tidal mud flats. It is situated 1,150 m. due ^{East} West of Tepe Chahah described below, and 2 km. from the village of Kumbil, and from its position was clearly concerned with maritime activities. The other, 600 m. by 400 m. is 5 m. high, and is covered with large quantities of clam shells and Sassanian sherds. It is situated 1.3 km. South West of the village of Minau and 15 km. West of Minab.

300 m. to the South of this last site is the largest Islamic site in Minab. Partly covered by sand dunes and by cultivation, its maximum extent is 1,100 m. by 800 m. and its height, 4 m.. The surface pottery is from earliest Islamic times to the 9th century A.H.. H 36?

Another large site, called Qaleh-i Saravan, is situated to the East of the village of Gurazu, 14 km. South East of Minab. Pottery covers an area of 800 m. by 500 m. The predominance of scratched and white bodied glazed wares suggest that the site was occupied in the 5th and 6th centuries A.H.. H 120-131

The mound of Chahah is of particular interest. It is situated on mud flats 20 km. South East of Minab and 3.5 km. West of the village of Kumbil, closely approached by tidal water. In this inhospitable environment a large H 03

settlement was constructed of burnt brick and of stone, some, sandstones and beach rock brought from the mountains behind Minab and others, volcanics brought by sea from Muscat. The mounding, which rises to a maximum of 2.5 m. above the mud flats, covers an area of 800 m. by 500 m., though a sea wall 2.5 m. thick with a jetty encloses a much larger area. This city, built with much labour, could not have been inhabited more than 100 years, since the pottery, including large quantities of Chinese celadon, must all belong to the 7th century A.H. and testify to a considerable trade with the Far East. The ruins of Chahah should certainly be identified with those of Old Hormuz, abandoned in 700 A.H. for the island of Jerun, New Hormuz. On my latest visit to the site I observed that the mounds had been robbed for the removal of building stone. Attached to this report is a plan of the site which, it is my hope, will be of assistance in the preservation of this monument.

The last major site in the Minab oasis is situated 12 km. West South West of Minab, near the village of Gishnau. A sandy mound covers an area of 1,150 m. by 650 m.. On the eastern end of this the pottery date exclusively from the 3rd to 4th centuries A.H.. On the rest of the mound this material is mixed with later pottery down to the 8th century A.H.. 450 m. away across a water course a mound called Tump-i Surkh clearly represented the richer portion of the town. The ruins of baked brick and stone buildings, some plaster mortared, stand 4.5 m. high in an area of 300 m. by 250 m.. This mound, like that of Chahah, is unfortunately currently being robbed for its stones and bricks. A plan is attached to this report.

c) The Region of Bandar-i Tahiri.

Twenty-five Islamic sites of small size were investigated within 30 km.

of Siraf. Of these, no fewer than twenty had on the surface white tin glazed pottery characteristic of the period of the greatest prosperity of Siraf in the 3rd to 4th centuries A.H., and were clearly involved in the wealth of this port.

On the coast 95 to 115 km. South East of Siraf twenty-one Islamic sites were investigated near the villages of Bostanu, Shivu, and Neran. The largest of these, called locally Borogla, was 700 m. West of the hamlet of Ziarat and stretched along the sea shore for 950 m., with a maximum width of 400 m., and had pottery of the 1st to 4th centuries A.H.. 1.5 km. South West of Gavbandi town, inland from Shivu, a Sassanian mound called Tal-i Pargu, 250 m. by 150 m. in size rises 7 m. high and clearly represents the ruins of some substantial buildings.

d) The Bushehr Peninsula.

Eighty-one sites were investigated in the Bushehr Peninsula. Two had Pre-Achaemenid pottery on the surface. Twenty-six had Achaemenid or Sassanian pottery, and the remainder were Islamic. Most of the sites investigated were very small.

However, four sites are worthy of note. Between the villages of Rishahr and Ziarat a low site 1,100 m. in length and over 800 m. in width was covered in pottery from Sassanian times to the 9th century A.H.. South of the village of Sabzabad Sassanian and Early Islamic pottery was unevenly scattered over an area of 1,200 m. by 500 m.. To the South of Halileh, stretching across the narrow peninsula from the eastern shore, a site of 850 m. by 350 m. of possibly Achaemenid and Sassanian date has a smaller site of 3rd to 4th centuries Hegira

overlying a portion of it. 450 m. to the West of this site, extending along the West shore of the peninsula is a mound 700 m. by 250 m. in size with Achaemenid and Sassanian pottery on the surface. 6 km. North of Halileh on the road to Bushehr a small site of 80 m. by 120 m. has prehistoric painted pottery of Ubaid date on the surface.

PLAN OF THE ISLAMIC SITE OF TUMP-I SURIKH IN THE MINAB OASIS

Schwaberi. 18

The year of the foundation of the Hornumir hufstern is not known - the earliest fixed point is the death of the 12th king in 1278

According to Mario Pato. 1273 it was used as an export point for Denmarks and Hoves. and also Gold, Silver, Copper, Iron, Lead, Tin + Wax. Exports of silk, gems, jewels, pearls, ivory and brocade.

10 km S-W of Munich - 15 km from the coast are the remains of a long mole which are the remains of the medieval port of Hornum

The merchants forced the men to Hornum.

Hornum trading colony with a temple in Bander Cobbers today.